

FEATURES OF LAND MARKET INFRASTRUCTURE

Ubaydov Mirshod Ismailovich

Chief Specialist of the State Asset Management Agency

Annotation. This article discusses the specific features of the land market infrastructure. Land market infrastructure is a set of organizational and legal forms, various institutions, and organizations that serve the land market and ensure its functioning.

Key words: land, market, mechanism, economy, distribution, investment, resource.

YER BOZORI INFRASTRUKTURISINING XUSUSIYATLARI

Ubaydov Mirshod Ismoilovich

Davlat aktivlarini boshqarish agentligi bosh mutaxassisi

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada yer bozori infratuzilmasining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Yer bozori infratuzilmasi - bu yer bozoriga xizmat qiluvchi va uning faoliyatini ta'minlovchi tashkiliy-huquqiy shakllar, turli muassasalar, tashkilotlar yig'indisidir.

Kalit so'zlar: yer, bozor, mexanizm, iqtisodiyot, taqsimot, investisiya, resurs.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ РЫНКА ЗЕМЛИ

Убайдов Миршод Исмаилович

Главный специалист Агентства по управлению

государственными активами

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются особенности инфраструктуры рынка земли. Инфраструктура рынка земли представляет собой совокупность организационно-правовых форм, различных институтов и организаций, обслуживающих рынок земли и обеспечивающих его функционирование.

Ключевые слова: земля, рынок, механизм, экономика, распределение, инвестиции, ресурс.

Introduction. Analysis of numerous definitions of the essence of market infrastructure allows us to conclude that it is a necessary condition for the placement and functioning of all social production and the normal life of people. However, such a definition, while correct in principle, is not complete enough to characterize infrastructure as a sector of the economy [1]. First, from many definitions it is difficult to determine which range of sectors that are identical in functional purpose to include infrastructure; secondly, the combination of auxiliary and additional production with infrastructure makes it difficult to distinguish between production itself and infrastructure, since it is difficult to distinguish auxiliary and additional sectors from these definitions [2]. It is very difficult to define the concept of "infrastructure" because it depends on the specific object of study, the technology of its operation, and the degree of influence of other objects [3].

In general, market infrastructure, in terms of its origin or nature, is nothing more than an institutionalized transaction. Intermediation services are a product of the land market infrastructure [4]. It is appropriate to distinguish two main functions of market-type infrastructure (or market infrastructure in a broader sense) according to the nature of the market economy:

- a) ensuring the smooth functioning of economic relations and interactions between market economy entities;
- b) regulating the movement of commodity and money flows.

Thus, the economic infrastructure of the market has a significant impact on the functioning of the entire economic system. Since the land market is an integral part of the market of production factors, it is appropriate to distinguish the infrastructure of the land market as its subsystems [5].

The infrastructure of the land market is a set of organizational and legal forms, various institutions and organizations that serve the land market and ensure its operation. The more developed the infrastructure and various institutions in the market, as well as the more diverse the conditions for transactions in the land market, the more developed it will be. Due to the availability of infrastructure, business relations between land market entities are conducted on a targeted basis.

The functions of the land market infrastructure have been expanded to include:

- participation in self-regulation of the land market by equalizing land prices;
- minimization of risks, redistribution of risks, reduction of uncertainty in the market environment;
- provision of relevant services to land market entities:
- assistance to land market entities in realizing their economic interests;
- organizational registration of trade and economic relations of business partners;
- provision of legal, financial, insurance, and control services;
- study of market conditions, competitors, intermediaries, and consumers;
- mediation in obtaining loans and establishing business relationships;
- use of the capabilities of information support, computer networks, and communication facilities.

It should be noted that the economy clearly shows the existence of direct and inverse relationships between the land market and its infrastructure.

Market infrastructure includes a huge number of elements that are closely interconnected and together play an important role in the economy. The composition of infrastructure networks is characterized by a certain flexibility, depending on the level of territorial formation, their specific features.

Various researchers identify various elements in the infrastructure of the land market, sometimes narrowing it, sometimes excessively expanding it. The most

extensive list of elements of the market infrastructure, including the land market, is given in the monograph of L.A. Ibragimov. These include not only financial, information, legal organizations, but also regulatory organizations, the transport system, the communication system, the fuel and energy complex, and others.

The activities of general-purpose institutions are usually aimed at performing a certain function in all markets. All these organizations are created to meet the needs of all markets, an organizational system that reflects supply and demand.

The subjects of general-purpose institutions in the land market are:

- marketers, public relations and advertising specialists engaged in the promotion of objects and services in the market;
- information and analytical publications and other mass media specializing in the land market and the real estate market in general;
- specialists in the field of personnel training and advanced training.

Special-purpose institutions, unlike general-purpose institutions, operate only in the field of the land market; and serve to ensure its uninterrupted operation.

To develop the infrastructure of the land market, systematic work should be carried out in the following areas:

1) lack of market data and ignorance of the rules for processing transactions. Citizens and organizations face a number of difficulties in carrying out operations, including lack of data and ignorance of the rules for processing transactions, high prices and conditions for their implementation, conditions for the sale and lease of land. The difficulty lies in the fact that due to the absence of established market prices, quasi-market prices are still used in land transactions: cadastral, regulatory or so-called "market", even these settlement prices or the rules for their formation are not open to everyone;

2) high prices for land and the difficulty of transactions. high prices for processing transactions concluded by a specialist and the difficulties in their implementation.

3) the restriction of the agricultural land market in the future and the lack of land withdrawal from agricultural circulation as an incentive for turnover at present. Agricultural lands are declaratively protected by the state, but there is no real mechanism to protect the land from being taken away from agricultural production. Many people are buying land for purposes other than agriculture.

Land market development trends are institutionalized through the formation of an institutional infrastructure. The goals of creating institutions in the markets of production resources, which include the land market, are:

- 1) strengthening the market power of specific owners;
- 2) influencing resource prices;
- 3) redistributing the income of owners;
- 4) redistributing the resources themselves according to their areas of use;
- 5) redistributing property to specific groups of resources.

The main shortcomings of the land policy implemented so far are as follows:

The first is that until recently it was not separately identified as an independent direction, but was implemented within the framework of general mechanisms for regulating land relations and real estate turnover.

The second drawback is the abundance of legislative norms, inconsistency, gaps in regulating the circulation of land shares, protecting agricultural lands from inappropriate, irrational use, especially valuable lands, as well as low awareness among the population of the specifics of land rights of the rural population, which are often used by squatters.

The third drawback is that little attention has been paid to land management as the main tool of land management. The issue of replacing the term “land management” with the category of “situational studies” has even been discussed.

The fourth drawback is the insufficient development of modern methods of monitoring and controlling land use.

In general, it can be noted that during the years of socio-economic

transformation, along with endless administrative reforms, there was a body responsible for accounting and control, but the executive branch did not create an optimal method of using land resources.

In improving the organizational and legal elements of the land market infrastructure, the Cadastral Agency should provide organizational and methodological guidance on land registration and control over their use.

Thus, the following measures should be taken to develop the organizational and legal elements of the land market infrastructure:

- the current law on land management should be seriously revised, distinguishing between two main types of land management: state (by decision and at the expense of the state) and initiative (by decision and at the expense of rights holders and their associations).

- formation of a state order for large land management projects that are unattractive for private entrepreneurship;

- subsidizing part of the costs of land management from the city budget.

The cadastral and market value of land can differ significantly. For example, in subsidized areas where there are no purchase and sale transactions, the market value can be several times lower. It is clear that in this case it is unprofitable for the bank to accept an object with an overvalued price as collateral. The main difficulty for the appraiser in such work is to search for offers for transactions on comparable objects, since the main issue for the bank is the liquidity of the object, the ability to sell it at the price indicated on the market. It turns out that even if the value of the land by income is higher than the value obtained by the method of comparison of sales, the final value will be higher according to the results of the comparison, that is, it will be lower than the value of the land.

Conclusion. Comprehensive implementation of the proposed directions will create the infrastructure that will ensure the development of the land market in Uzbekistan at the current stage.

References

[1] Abdurashid A., Muhammadbek M. Regulation of the Diversification of the Use of the District Land Fund through the General Scheme //Design Engineering. – 2021. – C. 2565-2581.

[2] Altiev, A., & Mahsudov, M. (2020). Improvement of the regulation mechanisms of the land use diversification. International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. ISSN, 9752366.

[3] Sultanovich, A. A., & Ugli, M. M. D. (2019). Methods of forecasting and management of land fund diversification in local areas. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering, 8(3), 403-411.

[4] Altiev, A. S., & Mahsudov, M. D. (2019). REPRODUCTION CYCLE OF LAND. Central Asian Problems of Modern Science and Education, 3(4), 96-102.

[5] AR Babajanov, MD Mahsudov. Diversification of land fund in the district. Monograph. LAP Lambert Academic Publishing, 77-78